

Applied Linguistics-Digital Platforms Whatsapp and Telegram Users Behavioral Tendency

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Abstract: The present research study aimed to deliver an overlook based on the behavioral tendency of the users of WhatsApp and Telegram when applying linguistics into communicative messages. Through a particularized literature framework, the research study has displaced some notable influencer tech-application factors and applied linguistics specificity that are currently characterizing WhatsApp and Telegram Interpersonal Communication backgrounds. The research study was conducted by following suitable research protocols. This prospect involved the revision of specialized materials such as publications and webpages focused on the subject presented. Database from a survey piloted among university students formed part of this research criterion. The survey served to measure public' level of favoritisms applied linguistics text, voice, and picture WhatsApp and Telegram messages. This study is very useful for scholars interested in Linguistics and Applied Linguistics Studies.

Keywords: Behaviorisms; Linguistics; Technology; Communication

INTRODUCTION

The involvement of technology in all areas of our societies has definitely transformed the way we behave ourselves, and when communicating one with each other through technology, our intellectual competences go lengthwise with our preferable approaches. According to (Stephen, 2020) the pace of technological advancement shows no signs of slowing, and we certainly won't be returning to simpler times barring catastrophic turns of events. Going digital is the only way to keep up with the rapid pace of the modern world. Although numerous researcher studies have been conducted addressing technology, linguistics and communication issues (Akmajian, 2010); (Berger, 2008); (Croft, 2015); (Golonka, Tare & Bonilla, 2017); (Halliday, 2004); (Knapp, 2002); (Pearce, 2008); (Tardanico, 2012); (Thompson, 2002). From the standpoint of uniqueness view none is meant to deliver an overlook based on the behavioral tendency of the users of WhatsApp and Telegram when applying linguistics into communicative messages.

The idea that all behaviors are acquired through conditioning and conditioning occurs through interaction with the environment; it is consistent with the fact that even though behaviorists generally accept the important role of heredity in determining behavior, they focus primarily on environmental events (Araiba Sho, 2019). So, when it comes to use the Digital Platforms WhatsApp and Telegram for accomplishing language interchanges; the tech-communication-environment facilitated by these digital mediums tends to stimulate public' level of favoritisms applied linguistics text, voice, and picture messages. A communication form through which the intellectual competences of these users go along with their preferable approaches in doing it. It is believed that one of the reasons for which people behave this way when conducting interpersonal communication settings is related to Applied Linguistics (Joel, 2020). So, as this practice necessary involves the use of language and its main cores; for us understanding what it has been communicated, it would have to be necessary to look at some of the Tech-Application Factors and Applied Linguistics Specificity that are currently characterizing these Interpersonal Communication Approaches.

Interpersonal Communication-Influencer Tech-Application Factors Backgrounds

Although the tech design of the Digital Platforms WhatsApp and Telegram differs no much; the tech-features [text messages and voice messages, make voice and video calls, and share images, documents,] provided by them to facilitate communication practices are alike. So, this framework provides users the opportunity to conduct interpersonal communication approaches through what has become a [personalized manner], and which can be observed when these users exchanging typing, voice, and picture communicative linguistic messages respectively.

Interpersonal Communication-Applied Linguistics Specificity Backgrounds

Some of the applied linguistics specificity that one can find when analyzing WhatsApp and Telegram interpersonal communication background are those related to the [Lack of punctuation]; [Inferring communication motives by substituting lexicon and syntax words for self-visualization]; [Applying self-direct speeches by using phonetical variants].

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Based on the above-allegations which anyone can confirm by examining WhatsApp and Telegram Interpersonal Communication settings; pragmatically speaking I would say that we are currently dealing with a behavioral communication tendency that is definitely changing the way we communicate, and the fact that this subject-matter is not yet scientifically included into the field of Applied Linguistics, makes it a research subject-matter to be considered from the perspective of Syntactic and Semantic and Pragmatic.

Although traditional tools still make their way into communication approaches; by being exposed for the last three decades to a rapid development of the Digital Era, it should not be a surprise that our intellectual competences go along with our preferable approaches when Applied Linguistics through Digital Platforms.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology strategies used in this research-study helped to present the facts of the elements accessible in the manuscript. It has focused on collecting, analyzing, and mixing both quantitative and qualitative data in order to best address the literature framework which is based on 1) Research methodology. 2) Subject matter domain. 3) Results and discussion. This suitable research protocols prospect involved the revision of specialized materials such as publications and webpages focused on the subject presented. Database from a survey piloted among university students formed part of this research criterium. By employing these principles of research techniques; the study began gathering and analyzing data from a series of research-studies and Webpages focused on the subject investigated. The collection of both data has been appropriately displaced according to the literature of the research study presented. The first under the Introduction heading part and the second under the heading Biography. The data collected from the survey given to university students is shown below in the figures 1-6.

[Figure 1]

[Figure 2]

[Figure 3]

How often do you use WhatsApp?
48 responses

[Figure 4]

How often do you use Telegram?
48 responses

[Figure 5]

When using WhatsApp and Telegram to communicate with a person, I used to use language voice and pictured messages
48 responses

[Figure 6]

When using WhatsApp and Telegram to communicate with a person I do not seriously take into account applied linguistics rules
48 responses

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Thanks to the methodology implemented to conduct this research-study, a rational view based on communication behavioral tendency when using the Digital Platforms WhatsApp and Telegram to accomplish Interpersonal Communication settings has been displaced in an explicated manner for readers to understand the aim of the research-study, which has been to deliver an overlook based on the behavioral tendency of the users of WhatsApp and Telegram when applying linguistics into communicative messages. Thus, as a point of departure the research-study has outlined some notable influencer tech-application factors and applied linguistics specificness that are currently characterizing WhatsApp and Telegram Interpersonal Communication backgrounds. These insights are based on observations when using these digital platforms to exchange communicative text, voice, and picture messages, being the use of emojis one of the most preferred choices according to these observations, perhaps a behavior conditioned to the human visual-oriented trait. In sustaining this regard and amplifying the research-study range, a survey was conducted among university students. The statements in the questionnaire were set to measure scenically the public' level of favoritisms applied linguistics text, voice, and picture WhatsApp and Telegram messages. The questionnaire was comprised of different, and separated Google-form sections to avoid plagiarisms and as such increase confidentially on the data collected. Even though the research-study was limited to assignment a reduce number of university students from a language course conducted by the Faculty of Applied Communication (FAC), Multimedia University (MMU), Malaysia; it was possible to gather statistics insights that clearly show the intended purpose for which/and how the system of measurement was set.

All the insights shown throughout the research-study literature framework are valuable not only for their applied linguistics and communication implications, but for what they represent in terms of future research-activities. From the perspective of Applied Linguistics and Communication, the language used by the users of the Digital Platforms WhatsApp and Telegram when conducting Interpersonal Communication approaches seems to be reliable with the concept of language as a system that consists of the development, acquisition, maintenance and use of complex systems of communication. From the perspective of behaviorisms, the user's digital tendency preferences matter, and from the perspective of Digital Platforms, WhatsApp and Telegram are not the only ones to be explored in all these regards.

At present, it is yet unknown how the use of WhatsApp and Telegram, among many other Digital Platforms could be impacting the field of Applied Linguistics when using them to forthcoming interpersonal communication settings. So, looking at this subject matter from behaviorism perspectives, it could lead us to think in mind about the potentiality that this specific field has in terms of analyzing communication behavioral patterns associated with the huge exposure of technology we have been experienced for the last decades.

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CONCLUSSION

Generally, this research-study has focused on behavioral tendency when using linguistics into communicative WhatsApp and Telegram messages. Based on this aim, one could say that the manuscript presented contains significant literature sources corresponding to the main objective of the research study. The data presented in the manuscript contextualize clearly the subject-matter-domain exposed, in conjunction with which the study has presented remarkable and credential researcher views on the subject discussed and added new finding. The manuscript is a valuable contribution to the field of Applied Linguistics in Communication. Thus, it lets at the disposition of the readers and the specialized critics for its evaluation.

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INTERNET ACREDITATED WEBPAGES

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